

EBFMC25-OP-23 · The Relationship Between Caregiver Burden for Elderly Patients; Caregiver Muscle Strength, Nutrition and Sleep Status

 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15807766>

Oral Presentation #23 was presented at the 3rd International Eastern Black Sea Family Medicine Congress, held in Ordu, Türkiye, on May 22–24, 2025, and is part of the proceedings titled: *Proceedings of the 3rd International Eastern Black Sea Family Medicine Congress*.

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: The elderly population, defined as individuals aged 65 and over, is growing rapidly worldwide. This demographic shift is leading to an increased burden on caregivers, who are essential in assisting elderly patients (Bag Soytaş et al., 2023; Soysal & Smith, 2024). In our study, we aim to determine the burden of caregivers providing care for elderly patients.

Materials and Methods: Our study was conducted from March 2023 at Bezmialem Vakif University Faculty of Medicine Hospital, focusing on caregivers of hospitalized patients aged 65 and over. After collecting personal information, we used the Caregiver Burden Scale (CBS) for caregiver burden, the Mini Nutritional Assessment Test (MNAT) and Healthy Eating Attitude Scale for nutritional status, and the Epworth Sleepiness Scale (ESS) and Insomnia Severity Index (ISI) for sleep status. For muscle strength, a handgrip dynamometer was applied to the arm three times, and the maximum result was evaluated (Loi et al., 2014).

Results: To date, the study has enrolled 100 volunteer caregivers, comprising 79 females and 21 males, with a mean age of 50.5 years. According to the MNAT, the prevalence of undernutrition among participants is 48%. The ESS indicates a daytime excessive sleepiness prevalence of 12%, while the ISI reveals a moderate insomnia rate of 10%. Additionally, the handgrip test shows muscle weakness rates of 5% in females and 4% in males. When comparing total scores among participants, after adjustment for all confounders, a negative correlation was still observed between CBS and the MNAT, and a positive correlation was found between CBS and the ISI ($p < 0.05$) (Kulkarni et al., 2025; Perez et al., 2022).

Conclusion: Caregiver burden is linked to poor nutrition and sleep disturbances. Therefore, the sleep and nutrition status of caregivers should be regularly monitored, and necessary measures should be taken (Bag Soytaş et al., 2023; Kulkarni et al., 2025).

PEER REVIEW STATEMENT

This paper has undergone a double-blind peer review process and has been approved by the scientific committee of the conference.

KEYWORDS

Caregiver burden, elderly patients, nutrition, sleep status, muscle strength

CONFLICT OF INTEREST DECLARATION

There is no commercial, financial, or personal conflict of interest in this study.

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